

Deliverable D.Y.1.1
Data Management Plan (1st revision)

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H-SEARCH
Heritage Science Elastic Archives

 <https://rdm.kikirpa.be/projects/h-search>

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DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Impulse action call

INFRA-FED 2022

Compulsory document – must be completed

The present DMP form was designed for research projects. Some fields might not be applicable for research infrastructure projects. It is nevertheless requested to indicate all essential information that is relevant and applicable to the RI project.

This template corresponds to section **4.3.1 Data Management Plan** of your proposal.

FOREWORD

WHAT IS UNDERSTOOD AS RESEARCH DATA?

Research data are the evidence that underpin the answer to research questions and can be used to validate findings. Data can be quantitative information or qualitative statements collected by researchers in the course of their work by experimentation, observation, modelling, interview or other methods, or information derived from existing evidence.

For the purpose of BELSPO's data management policy, research data also includes digital information extracted from physical objects such as scientific and archaeological collections, physical arts works or biobanks.

Software is not included in the definition. BELSPO recognises that software (algorithms, scripts and codes developed by researchers in the course of their work) may be necessary to access and interpret data. In such cases, the data management plan needs to address how information about such items will be made available.

WHY IS A DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN NECESSARY?

Data Management Plans document and sustain a research project by explaining how it deals with copyright / open access requirements and ethical issues, and describe the plan for acquisition, long-term data preservation and sharing modes. They contribute to increasing the impact and visibility of research data, and ensure that the way handled data comply with the Open Data principle applied by BELSPO.

WHAT IS EXPECTED FROM THE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN?

The Data Management Plan (DMP) should describe how a researcher **deal with the collected data before, during and after the project**. It is a key element of a good data management.

As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (**FAIR**), the DMP shall include information on:

- how the data will be collected,
- the type, size and format of the generated data,
- when, where and in what format the data will be made accessible
- how the data will be curated and preserved for ulterior use (including after the end of the project).

It will clearly specify which categories of users are likely to benefit from access to the data.

The DMP must also contain information regarding the legal and ethical aspects of data.

In this respect, researchers shall use to the maximum existing platforms having the highest standard of preservation, curation, deposit and reuse.

INFORMATION REGARDING THE PROPOSAL

PROJECT ACRONYM	H-SEARCH
PROJECT TITLE	Heritage Science Elastic Archives

1. WILL DATA BE COLLECTED, REUSED AND/OR GENERATED?

Please select the adequate answer(s) taking into account the following concepts:

- Data content:*
Refers to the type of data regarding what it contains. E.g. numeric (databases, spread sheets), textual (documents), image, audio, video, mixed media...
- Data format:*
Refers to the technical format of data; to the way in which the data is encoded for storage, often reflected by the filename extension. For example: pdf, xls, doc, txt, rdf...
Whenever possible, give preference to open and standard formats as they facilitate sharing and long-term re-use of data.
- Data volume:*
You may roughly estimate this using the following categories: From 0 – 10GB; From 10 – 100 GB; From 100 – 1000 GB; More than 1000 GB.

<p>1.1. My proposal will...</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> COLLECT DATA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> REUSE EXISTING DATA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> GENERATE NEW DATA
<p><i>Please describe:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Which data you will collect/reuse/generate How data will be collected / from which source it will be reused / how will it be generated Its content, technical format and estimated volume. Any existing constraints regarding its use. 	
<p>Within H-SEARCH a distinction must be made between three main data categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> closed and centrally stored intervention dossiers (pre-archive) created archival packages (SIPs, AIPs, DIPs) project data (meeting reports, deliverables, publications) <p>The closed and centrally stored intervention dossiers can be classified under <u>1. Collected/reused data</u>, whereas the created archival packages and project data belong to <u>2. Newly created data</u>.</p>	

1. Collected / reused data

1.1. Intervention dossiers

H-SEARCH largely relies on **existing closed intervention dossiers** for the archiving and preservation part of the project. The data in a typical intervention dossier are very diverse and depend on the type of object being studied. During the time span of an intervention, an object is usually examined by many researchers from the different units of KIK/IRPA: the Documentation department will take photographs, perform scientific imaging and make art historical observations, the laboratories will do material studies resulting in images, analytical data and reports, and the conservation studios will create technical images, condition and conservation reports. All these types of data - stored in a variety of open and closed formats - will be collected in intervention dossiers. **Nowadays, an intervention dossier can be seen as a physical folder, a digital folder on the institutional network share or both (hybrid).**

KIK/IRPA scientific archive consists of approximately **20.789 intervention dossiers** in different forms (physical, digital, hybrid). The annual growth rate is 3%. As for the handling of closed intervention files there are currently **several parallel - and intertwined - practices:**

Closed intervention dossiers in a mixed environment

The official protocol for closed intervention dossiers is to return the paper output to the dossiers team where they are physically archived. The digital output, however, remains in the project folder of the cells or researchers involved, **resulting in a mixed environment where ongoing and closed intervention dossiers reside together in an often unorganised manner.** In the long run, this situation can be harmful. The main reason is that nothing is stopping a researcher from modifying the data – that have been previously labelled as ‘closed’. This practice violates the principle of integrity, one of the four cornerstones in the archival sciences.

Stored intervention dossiers

During the HESCIDA project, **a pre-archive has been created** in order to counter the above-mentioned issue and to centralise and store – according to a best-effort approach – closed digital-born intervention dossiers. Besides solving historically grown problems concerning the management of data in KIK/IRPA’s research units, the pre-archive also acts as an intermediate step to transfer closed and archived intervention dossiers to the public repository, accessible via the online catalogue [BALaT](#). The digitally archived intervention dossiers are located on a separate share. The intervention dossiers in the pre-archive are characterised by their **read-only status** and **organised structure**.

In addition to the pre-archive, an archive depot for the paper intervention dossiers – created since 1948 – acts as a physical storage location. The physically archived intervention dossiers are organized in shelves in an allocated room (250m²) with adapted temperature and relative humidity control.

The result of these parallel practices is a series of mixed environments for each KIK/IRPA unit, consisting of ongoing and closed (but not always digitally or physically centralised) dossiers. H-SEARCH aims to harmonise these mixed environments.

Handling intervention files in H-SEARCH

The ingest in the pre-archive is a work-in-progress. It is currently populated with approximately 230 digitally stored dossiers and increases in size daily. The pre-archive is considered as a prerequisite step, serving as central storage location. During the H-SEARCH project this pre-archive will transform into an **improved archive that adheres to archival principles and standards and that will extend over time**. This means that the present **intervention dossiers in the pre-archive will be taken as a basis for the preservation and archiving actions** described in WP.2. Besides, a small selection (based upon specific criteria disclosed in WP.1) of closed intervention dossiers, that have not yet been subjected to archival care, will also become eligible for long-term preservation and archiving efforts within H-SEARCH.

Brief outline:

Number of existing intervention dossiers	ca. 20.789 intervention dossiers in total (and still growing)
Form	physical (on paper), hybrid, digital-born, digitized (ad hoc by DIGIT)
Types of content	<ul style="list-style-type: none">– administrative documents, scientific reports, documentation, analytical data (both raw and processed), images, sample information, ...– mix of structured and unstructured data
Formats for unstructured data	.docx, .pdf, .pdf/a
Formats for structured data	<ul style="list-style-type: none">– mostly closed or proprietary formats (.wdx, .drm, .bkf, ...)– possibility to export proprietary formats to more open (e.g. .spc) and human-readable formats (e.g. JCAMP-DX) depending on the software used– open formats (.csv, .xlsx, .json, ...)
Image formats	.raw, .jpg, .tiff, .png
Volume intervention files	<ul style="list-style-type: none">– <u>Unorganised storage on fileserver (researchers)</u> – mix of ongoing and closed dossiers: estimated amount of 10 TB– <u>Centralised storage in the pre-archive (archivists)</u>: approximately 450 intervention dossiers 900 GB– <u>Archived on paper (archivists)</u>: 1500m– <u>Selected for H-SEARCH</u>: 450 intervention dossiers + extra amount to be determined * <p>* The DMP will be updated accordingly.</p>
IPR statement	CC-BY (reference to KIK/IRPA required)

1.2. Existing inventories

A protocol for the evaluation, prioritisation and selection of closed intervention dossiers – that are in urgent need of archival care – will be developed in WP.1. To create such a protocol, already existing inhouse inventories, such as the “[Topstukken](#)” list (Flemish masterpieces) and the “[Inventaire du Patrimoine culturel mobilier](#)” will be consulted.

1.3. Existing internal services

Under the hood, a number of internal services have been set up that improve the organisation and documentation of interventions.

- General metadata on intervention dossiers is documented in the collection management system, in which the objects, library collection and persons and institutions database are also documented. Currently this is Axiell Adlib CMS but will soon be migrated to **Axiell Collections**.
- Photographs (official, samples, action images) will be managed and annotated via a bespoke **digital assets management system** (DAMS) in the future. The DAMS internally stores the images on disk and the metadata in a MongoDB database.
- A bespoke open-source documentation platform, **MetaHub**, will be used to document the intervention dossiers in detail and in particular the individual datasets within those dossiers and samples taken in the context of a dossier. MetaHub uses JSON schemas to adapt dynamically for the type of data to be described and stores all metadata in a MongoDB database. The datasets itself are currently stored in the pre-archive.
- Data and metadata from all different sources will be aggregated and enriched in a **Elasticsearch cluster**, which forms the backbone of the new BALaT knowledge platform and its API.

H-SEARCH will build on top of these existing services.

1.4 NLP algorithms

Besides the preservation and archiving component in H-SEARCH, another goal is to integrate multilingual search capabilities by using Natural Language Processing (NLP), OCR and Elasticsearch for digital-born and digitised intervention dossiers. It contributes to the knowledge hub that BALaT will become (as stated in WP.3). During H-SEARCH word-embeddings (WE) (e.g. Word2Vec, GloVe) generated for NLP algorithms will be evaluated for text analysis, automated summarisation and automated translation based on Python libraries (e.g. BERT) and/or APIs (Google Translate, DeepL, etc.). The best options will be implemented within the existing Elasticsearch framework in order to enhance the existing search engine with intelligent (multilingual) search capabilities for full-text searching in the textual documents stored in archived intervention dossiers.

2. Newly generated data

Data	Filetype(s)	Source	Estimated size	Long-term
Publications, deliverables, meeting reports,docx, .pdf		0-10 GB	Yes

Documentation for archiving software solutions	.txt, .md		0-10 GB	Yes
Information packages (SIPs, DIPs and AIPs)	Container formats like BagIt, RO-Crate, OCFL, ...	Archiving software solutions (e.g. Archivematica, RODA, ...)	Depending on the complexity and amount of archived digital intervention dossiers: estimation of 100-1000 GB	Yes
Scripts (for automatization purposes)	Scripting language to be decided later. The DMP will be updated accordingly.		10-100 GB	Yes

2. HOW WILL YOU HANDLE LEGAL ISSUES?

Please answer the following statements taking into account the following concepts:

Legal issues: This includes personal data and intellectual property issues.

Regarding personal data, you must ensure when dealing with personal data that Data Protection Laws (i.e. GDPR) are complied with.

2.1. My proposal will use / process / store **personal data**:

YES

NO

If your answer is 'YES': shortly describe the kind of personal data.

Add the process and reference to your file in your host institution's privacy register.

Project data

The collection, processing and usage of personal information in project related data during the course of H-SEARCH can be considered as limited. Such data don't usually contain references to persons. If it is the case, closed access may be considered if its redaction and anonymisation (i.e. "data protection by design") could not be performed. On the level of 'project data' we can distinguish following personal information:

- Personal data (e.g. contact details) of team members and members of the follow-up committee obtained after consensual agreement.
- The project will hire new staff. As a result, *curricula vitae* and evaluation reports will be collected/generated and stored.

The storage location of project data within H-SEARCH will mainly be SharePoint (Microsoft Office 365), as access to members can easily be granted and it is a user-friendly platform to share information. However, personal data will not be stored and shared in this environment, they will be stored on the personal disk on the computer or OneDrive* of the Project Coordinator. The possibility to store such data on the institutions networked share – which is also frequently backed up and where one can have private folders – exists for both storage locations and will be exploited. The retention period will not exceed the legally determined duration.

** should be decided in the beginning of the project. The DMP will be updated accordingly.*

Intervention dossiers

During the lifespan of H-SEARCH, intervention dossiers will be preserved and archived. Intervention dossiers are created by researchers while performing their duties. Typically, in a dossier, there are reports containing applicants' personal data (predominantly name and address). Currently, there is a certain *modus operandi* for treating personal data that belong to private collectors. Contact details are registered in an internal database, named Coda, where an individual collection number for each applicant can be generated and used (rather than the name of the applicant) in the management tables (i.e. Excel files on SharePoint where researchers can add a new record when opening a new dossier).

Nevertheless, the private collector's number is not always consistently referred to in scientific reports. As a result, personal data remain visible. Subsequently, following specific actions are required:

- When an intervention file containing personal data is disseminated via the repository, the reports concerned will be anonymised (“data protection by design”). By anonymisation it is meant that the name and address are manually blacked out (redacted) via Adobe Pro. If anonymisation is not achievable, closed access will be opted for.
- When thirds consult an intervention file, the documents containing personal data are being removed (“data protection by design”).

Within WP.Y, Data management, attention will be drawn to the issue of treating applicants' personal data during preserving, archiving and disseminating actions. The output of T.Y.3. is a deliverable that will establish unambiguous guidelines that allows documentalists and archivists to handle cases in a consistent and lawful manner. Another goal of the deliverable is to look into “data protection by default” or “data minimisation”. As a scientific institute we have to ask ourselves: “Should we avoid using personal data from private persons in public scientific reports, as they are already stored in a non-public database?”.

Similarly, actions are currently being undertaken in KIK/IRPA to phase out the old management tables. The internal system based on shared Excel sheets will soon be replaced by a new application – named MetaHub – containing a database and user-friendly interface. MetaHub can

only be accessed via Single Sign-On (SSO, Keycloak). Outside the scope of this project, the outdated Coda will also be rewritten in the near future, so it will be in line with the GDPR legislation.

2.2. The work undertaken in the project will possibly result in **research data** with potential for **technology transfer** and **valorisation**: YES
 NO

If your answer is 'YES', your proposal must take into account possible intellectual property issues. Explain who will be the owner of the data (who will have the rights to control access). Indicate whether there will be intellectual property rights/restrictions for the data you created, and if applicable, describe how these will be managed.

Project members will exclusively work with data from the scientific archives of KIK/IRPA. As a result, KIK/IRPA can be considered as the owner of the research data created during H-SEARCH. However, not all data can be attributed to KIK/IRPA. Sometimes an intervention dossier may contain e.g. documentation obtained from other institutions. In the pre-archive, such data are placed in a folder named "external documentation". It is the rule that data that do not originate from KIK/IRPA will not be shared through the public repository.

The content of an internal digital archive differs from that of a public repository. A digital archive will hold data that are of great institutional value and therefore must follow legally agreed upon appraisal procedures in order to decide what to keep and what to eliminate. Whereas a public repository will disseminate data that have a more scientific value. Administrative documents, for example, might contain sensitive information and therefore not publicly available. Such documents are only archived internally. Because the OAIS Reference Model will be instantiated in the archival workflow (WP.2) during H-SEARCH project, several flows will need to be developed to transfer the information packages where they need to be stored*.

* The DMP will be updated accordingly.

Besides the collection of old and new intervention dossiers, much of the project output exists of reports and deliverables. These will be made available via the KIK-IRPA community on Zenodo using a CC-BY license.

2.3. Will agreements with 3rd parties restrict the dissemination or exploitation of the data the project will (re)use: YES
 NO

*If your answer is 'YES': explain which data are affected by this agreement
State the restrictions that are in place.*

Not applicable

3. HOW WILL YOU DOCUMENT YOUR DATA?

Please answer the questions/statements, taking into account the following information:

Data must comply, as much as possible with FAIR principles; it must be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. For this purpose, data must be accompanied by descriptive information in the form of metadata. Metadata is the information that describes, explains, locates, and /or makes the use of an information source easier to retrieve. Where metadata are in place, researchers are advised to use and mention metadata standards.

3.1. What documentation will be provided to enable understanding and reuse of the data collected / generated in this project?

Documentation is essential in order to fully comprehend research data that have been collected and generated during H-SEARCH. Software code will be provided with sufficient documentation. GitHub has the possibility to add documentation as well. Other documentation tools, like Confluence, may be adopted. As for reports and deliverables, a minimum of metadata is amassed and will be displayed in the front page of each report:

- File name / title
- Date
- Version
- Description
- Work package number
- Responsible person(s)
- Dissemination level

All existing data collected in intervention dossiers can be extensively documented in MetaHub, a bespoke documentation system, and a digital assets management system (DAMS). In other words, these two internal services fix and preserve the entire research context of an intervention that will eventually end up as a closed intervention dossier in the digital archive.

3.2. Metadata standards will be used:

- FOR ALL DATA
 FOR SOME DATA
 FOR NONE OF THE DATA

- *if your answer is 'for all data' or 'for some data', please describe in detail which standards will be used.*
- *if your answer is 'none of the data', please state in detail which metadata will be created to make the data easy/easier to find and reuse.*

The Dublin Core metadata standard will be used for grey literature. When data is deposited in Zenodo, a Dublin Core-based standard is mostly offered. All of this information is for now still kept within the documents and MetaHub and can therefore be completed in a provided metadata schema.

MetaHub is used to describe intervention dossiers, datasets and samples. It uses metadata schemas that are being discussed and generated in the DIGILAB community, in the interoperability and DIGILAB-related tasks in IPERION-HS and E-RIHS IP, and in the ICCROM HSAI project for samples. Whereas possible, those metadata schemas are based on existing conventions and standards within the communities for the specific techniques (e.g. IRUG for FTIR and Raman spectroscopy). All schemas in MetaHub can be mapped to Dublin Core, but additionally contain a lot of metadata characteristic of a particular type of data and that are essential to describe that data.

4. DATA STORAGE AND BACKUP DURING THE INFRA-FED PROJECT

Please answer the statements/questions, taking into account the following information. Note that you may choose one or more answers to statement 4.1.

Please give preference to the use of robust, managed storage with automatic backup, such as provided by IT support services of your home institution. Most research institutions have networked drives, which offer ample storage space and data security for most purposes.

Consider data protection, particularly if your data is sensitive – for example, containing personal data, politically sensitive information or information relating to religion and health. If this is your case, enquire with your institution's research support staff whether your intended storage solution meets your institution's data security policy.

4.1. The data will be stored in...	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institution Networked Research Storage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OTHER
<p><i>If your answer includes 'OTHER':</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specify which storage solutions you will use during the project, in addition to / instead of the institutional networked research storage. • Explain the reasons for using these solutions. E.g. because you need more space than offered by your institution; to facilitate data sharing with collaborators; or because your data requires additional security. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A separate share on the institutional network share (fileserver) is used as location for stored intervention dossiers (pre-archive). • In addition, a SharePoint (Microsoft Office 365) for H-SEARCH will be used to store and share newly created and living data of the project. A folder within the already existing data management SharePoint environment will be created. SharePoint has the possibility to also be backed up (see 4.2.). GDPR sensitive data will probably be stored on the personal OneDrive of the Project Coordinator (see 2.1. and 4.3). • Source code will be pushed to GitHub. KIK/IRPA is registered as an organisation on GitHub (https://github.com/kikirpa). • Virtual servers hosting the software solutions used and/or developed in the H-SEARCH project (OCR/full-text indexing, archival solution, ...) • The archival packages (SIP,AIP) resulting from the archival system will be stored locally and on long-term solutions such as LTP. 	
4.2. How will the data be backed up?	
<p>The project's virtual servers and the pre-archive on the institutional network share (fileserver) will be backed up daily in their entirety on one backup server on-premise and two backup servers off-site. Several incremental backup versions will be kept in the backup chain, using snapshots.</p> <p>Alerts will be sent upon failure to back up. Restore tests for the virtual servers will be scheduled using Veeam SureBackup to verify if backups can be restored successfully.</p> <p>The local on-premise back up and off-site backup of both the virtual servers and pre-archive differ in operating system, access rights and the software used for backup, to decrease the chance of compromise during a malware attack, as to not have the same types of exploits available on both backup systems that could be abused.</p> <p>The archival packages are kept locally (Fileserver) and sent to the LTPs by the default workflow. SharePoint will be back upped daily, using the O365 Synology back up software to pull in data incrementally from the Microsoft cloud from SharePoint to our on-premise server. It allows us to restore SharePoint completely or partially from a moment in time.</p>	

4.3. How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable (there are no sensitive data) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Default security of the institution networked research storage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Additional security measures
<i>If your answer is other than 'Not applicable': Describe the main risks and how these will be managed.</i>	
<p>Personal data are stored on the personal disk or personal OneDrive of the Project Coordinator of H-SEARCH. The possibility of using fileserver will be explored. If it is decided to use fileserver, permissions are set with a zero-trust strategy. This means that the IT staff enforces least privileges. Only staff that needs access, gets access.</p> <p>Access to services within the project will integrate KIK/IRPA's authorisation server (based on KeyCloak). Permissions for specific access to services or data, will be defined with user roles and several protocols for authorisation are supported.</p>	
4.4. What are the expected costs for data storage and backup during the project? How will these costs be covered?	
<i>Costs related to data storage and backup during the project can be covered by the project budget providing these are fully justified and relate to the project.</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Server virtual host that will run the virtual servers: in-kind by KIK/IRPA • Nutanix software: in-kind budget by KIK/IRPA • SharePoint Online: licenses provided in-kind by KIK/IRPA • Backup SharePoint: licenses provided in-kind by KIK/IRPA and will be switched to Synology O365 back up software in 2025. • Storage place for data on the institutional network share (fileserver): provided in-kind by KIK/IRPA • Backup server capacity (1 on-premise, 1 off-sites): provided in-kind by KIK/IRPA 	

5. DATA PRESERVATION IN THE LONG TERM - AFTER THE INFRA-FED PROJECT

Please answer the following questions/statements, taking into account the following information. Note that you may choose one or more answers to statement 5.2.

BELSPO expects the data generated during the project to be preserved (archived) in the long term, in as far as legal and contractual agreements allow. As rule of thumb, long-term storage is considered to be at least 10 years, unless legal provisions or discipline-specific guidelines dictate otherwise.

5.1. All data will be preserved in the long term (at least 10 years)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO
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If your answer is **'NO'**: clearly describe what data will be preserved long-term and what data will be destroyed for contractual, legal or regulatory purposes, or for physical preservation issues. Indicate how you will decide which data to keep.

As the services, created during H-SEARCH, will be integrated in KIK-IRPAs data management workflow, it is crucial to keep the projects' output and observations permanently. Deliverables give insight in the technical aspects of services and KIK/IRPA's workflow.

Personal data that are no longer considered to be kept, are permanently deleted, after H-SEARCH has ended.

5.2. The data will be archived within...

- Institution Networked Research Storage
- OTHER

If your answer includes **'OTHER'**: Specify which storage solutions you will use in the long term, in addition to/instead of the institutional networked research storage. Please explain the reasons for using these solutions.

- After H-SEARCH ends, data stored on SharePoint will be transferred to "Projects" at Fileserver where finished projects are being archived.
- The archival packages (SIP, AIP) generated by the archival system will need to be archived long-term by using the following solutions:
 - LTP: the long-term archiving solution managed by Belnet, will be used once the new platform is active after their migration between suppliers. Scripts will be made or modified to automatically ingest data into this platform
 - Fileserver

5.3. How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care in the long term?

- Not applicable (there are no sensitive data)
- Default security of the institution networked research storage
- Additional security measures

If your answer is **other than 'Not applicable'**: Describe the main risks and how these will be managed. Inquire with your institution's research support staff whether your intended storage solution meets your institution's data security policy if your research involves sensitive data.

- Only staff of the IT service and archival staff will have access to restore data from the LTP platform. As we use a platform (LTP) managed by Belspo, we are dependent upon their agreement with the current supplier of the LTP (Smals), in terms of who at Smals is allowed access to the ingested data.

5.4. What are the expected costs for data preservation in the long term?
How will these costs be covered?

Costs related to data preservation in the long term can be covered by the project budget providing these are fully justified and relate to the project.

- LTP: funding for LTP is provided and managed through Belspo and the DIGIT-program.

6. DATA SHARING AND REUSE

Please answer the following questions taking into account the following information:

As stated before, data must comply, as much as possible with FAIR principles; it must be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. It is thus important that you provide information regarding data sharing and reuse.

Data sets will be linked to the scientific publication they underpin and which have either been deposited in, or linked to Orfeo, BELSPO's central Open Access Repository for publications.

Note that the data available for sharing and reuse may differ from the preserved data, since there may be legal, IP, privacy or security related reasons preventing or restricting the access to data, or lacking of space for large data volumes to deposit them in a repository in its entirety. This could be the case for part or the entirety of data; in the short, mid or long term. For data requiring protection, BELSPO therefore observes the "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" principle. A staged approach will provide access for communities of certified users, adapting the degree of certification of users to the sensitivity of the data.

6.1. Are there any factors restricting or preventing the sharing or reuse of the data (e.g. agreements with 3rd parties):	<input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO
<p><i>If your answer is 'YES': explain which data are affected by this agreement. State the restrictions that are in place.</i></p>	
<p>Most of the data will be publicly available. If personal data are present into an intervention dossier or a deliverable, closed access shall be chosen and/or personal details may be redacted using Adobe Acrobat DC ("data protection by design").</p>	
6.2. Which data will be made available to the public?	<input type="checkbox"/> ALL <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SOME PART <input type="checkbox"/> NONE
<p><i>If your answer is 'SOME PART' or 'NONE':</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Indicate the restrictions on the sharing of the data (why can't it be shared)</i> • <i>Explain what data sharing agreement will be implemented</i> • <i>Explain what actions will be taken to overcome or to minimise restrictions.</i> 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project data (meeting reports, deliverables, publications) will be made available through the KIK-IRPA community on Zenodo. Personal data will not be shared. • Full-text searchable content of files in intervention files will be made publicly accessible through the BALaT knowledge platform. 	
6.3. Where/how will data be made available to the public?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Open Access repository <input type="checkbox"/> In a restricted access repository

	<input type="checkbox"/> Upon request by mail <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
<p><i>If your answer is other than 'Open Access repository': Indicate where and how access will be provided.</i></p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The archival packages created within H-SEARCH themselves will not be stored online, however most data contained in these packages will be available online through the repository managed by the HESCIDA-project. • Project data (deliverables, publications, presentations) will be made available through the KIK-IRPA community on Zenodo. • Full-text searchable content of files in intervention files will be made publicly accessible through the BALaT knowledge platform (ElasticSearch Cluster). • The majority of reports and deliverables will be ingested in OA repositories. Grey literature will be by default deposited into ORFEO, the Open Access Repository for Federal Organisations. Project data will be deposited on Zenodo. 	
6.4. When will data be made available to the public?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> As soon as corresponding communication(s) are published <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> After the project is finished <input type="checkbox"/> After the completion of the project (with embargo)
<p><i>If your answer is other than 'as soon as corresponding communication(s) are published': Indicate the reasons for the restrictions on the time release of data (embargo periods). For example, to publish, protect intellectual properties, or seek patents.</i></p>	
<p>Finished deliverables will become available as soon as possible.</p>	
6.5. Who will be able to access the data and under which conditions?	
<p>Everyone can access Zenodo. For reports and deliverables, a CC-BY license will be applied, meaning that the creator of the content must be "appropriately credited". Source code is consultable via GitHub. EUPL or MIT are two options for licensing software.</p>	
6.6. Which data will be made available for re-use?	<input type="checkbox"/> ALL <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SOME PART <input type="checkbox"/> NONE
<p><i>If your answer is 'SOME PART' or 'NONE': Indicate the restrictions on the re-use of the data. Explain what actions could be taken to overcome or to minimise restrictions.</i></p>	
<p>Everything is available for re-use, except for administrative data.</p>	
6.7. Under what license will be data shared for re-use?	<input type="checkbox"/> Creative Commons CCO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Creative Commons CC-BY <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

<i>If your answer is 'OTHER': Indicate which license will the data have for reuse, and why.</i>
Re-use of data is allowed, as long as the creator of the content is credited.
6.8. What are the expected costs for data sharing? How will these costs be covered?
<i>Costs related to data sharing can be covered by the project budget providing these are fully justified and relate to the project.</i>
The main outputs of this project will be reports and, to a lesser extent, software. The reports are mainly textual information that will be deposited on existing repositories such as Zenodo and ORFEO. The expected costs for this will be negligible.
Software will be deposited on GitHub, which is free of charge for public repositories.

7. RESPONSIBILITIES

Please answer the following questions/statements, taking into account the following information:

7.1. Who will be responsible for the data documentation & metadata?
<i>In case of the use of personal data, please note the name and contact data of the concerned data protection officers.</i>
Project coordinator of H-SEARCH together with the team members
7.2. Who will be responsible for data storage & back up during the project?
KIK/IRPA's IT service and the project coordinator of H-SEARCH
7.3. Who will be responsible for ensuring data preservation and sharing?
Archivist
7.4. Who bears the end responsibility for updating & implementing this DMP?
<i>Default response: The Principal Investigator (PI) bears the overall responsibility for updating & implementing this DMP.</i>
Project coordinator of H-SEARCH in collaboration with the data manager